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A Creative Folio

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Wrong Impressions

I never thought life would bring me despair,
After such a rhythmic and pretty moment.
Just a snap of weak fingers, the music turned blue.
By the time the beat alters, the dance floor is cleared.

Without turning back, fellows are left behind.
Voice inside me calls back to gaze at my fellow,
But it's really the time to empty the dance floor;
So much has to be done; without the prior beat.

Why did the rhythm have to end so soon?
Grooves on its mold, but suddenly deviated.
Our backs are turned, though not supposed to do so fast.

But perhaps, that's the way our destinies must take.
We knew each other less when the beat was on our will.
As fate would have it, we had to part ways.
As for some vague, nebulous circumstances,
We left each other with some wrong impressions.

Wrong impressions, never known guilty or not.
Wrong impressions, the innocent suffered the most.